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HOLISTIC APPROACH OF DERMATITIS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

Dermatitis is a big issue on health. Dermatitis was estimated to affect 334 million people globally. According to *Ayurveda* the main reason of dermatitis and its recurrence is faulty dietary habits and faulty life style. Due to these reasons *Dhosha* accumulates in the body and comes in contact with *Dushya* (*Twak, Rakta, Mamsa, Ambu*) and manifested as *vicharchika*. *Ubhay Marga Shodhana* by *Vamana* and *Virachana* (biopurification) is very important to expel the *Dosha* and purify the body. It also effective to break down *Dosh-Dushya Sammurchhana* of *vicharchika*. After break down of *sammurchhana*, *Dosha* can be treated easily with *Shamana* drugs. To prevent the recurrence of vitiation of *doshas shamana* drugs along with avoidance of causative factor is necessary (*Nidana parivarjanam*). Hence, classical approach of treating dermatitis provides fast and best relief in dermatitic symptoms but also reduces the chances of its recurrence. Thus, classical approach is essential part of management of Dermatitis.

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Introduction:

Dermatitis, also known as eczema, is a group of diseases that results in inflammation of the skin. These diseases are characterized by itchiness, red skin, and a rash. In cases of short duration there may be small blisters while in long-term cases the skin may become thickened. The area of skin involved can vary from small to the entire body¹.

Dermatitis is a group of skin conditions that includes atopic dermatitis, allergic contact dermatitis, irritant contact dermatitis, and stasis dermatitis. The exact cause of dermatitis is often unclear. Cases are believed to often involve a combination of irritation, allergy, and poor venous return. The type of dermatitis is generally determined by the person's history and the location of the rash. For example, irritant dermatitis often occurs on the hands of people who frequently get them wet. Allergic contact dermatitis, however, can occur following brief exposures to substances a person is sensitive to².

Prevalence of Dermatitis:

Dermatitis was estimated to affect 334 million people globally in 2013. Atopic dermatitis is the most common type and generally starts in childhood. In the United States it affects about 10-30% of people. Contact dermatitis is two times more common in females than males. Allergic contact dermatitis affects about 7% of people at some point in time. Irritant contact dermatitis is common, especially among people who do certain jobs; exact rates are unclear³.

Aims and objective:

To evaluate efficacy of holistic approach in the treatment of dermatitis.

Ayurvedic View on Dermatitis:

All the skin diseases in *Ayurveda* have been discussed under the broad heading of “*khustha*”, which are further divided in *Maha & Kshudrakushtha*⁴. *Vicharchika* is considered one of the *Kshudrakushtha* in *Ayurvedic texts*⁵. *Ayurvedic* classics have considered each type of *kushtha* to be a *Tridoshaja* manifestation⁶. Their

Doshik identity can be established on the basis of dominance of *Dosha* in the *Samprapti*. *vicharchika* is *kapha* dominant phenomenon⁷ In present study the dermatitis has been correlated with *vicharchika*.

सकण्डुपिडीकाश्यावाबहुस्रावाविचर्चिका (ch.chi. 7/30)⁸

Sakandu (extensive itching), *Pidika* (small blisters), *Shyavavarna* (hyperpigmentation),

Bahusrava(excessive oozing)

Causes of *Khustha* :

Specific etiology for *vicharchika* has been not described in any *Ayurvedic* texts. So it can be understood by general etiology of *khustha*. All causes of *khustha* can be considered under two main headings:

***Aharajahetu* – Faulty Diet / Dietetic Pattern:**

The most common *Hetu* (cause) of *kushtha* mentioned in all the *Samhitas* is *Aharaj Hetu*. *Mithya Ahara*, *VirodhiAnna* constitutes the major cause of *kushtha* . *Viruddha Aahara* (Dietetic incompatibilities) is described in detail as the cause of *kushtha*⁹ .

***Viharajahetu* – Faulty Lifestyle:**

Proper follow up of *Dincharya*, *Rutucharya*, *AacharRasayana*, *AaharaVidhiVidhana* and *Panchkarma* is important for maintenance of health. *ViharajHetu* like *Paap karma* or insult to those who are worth giving respect results in immediate aggravation and vitiation of *Tridosha*¹⁰ .

***Saptako Dravya Sangraha*:**

As per *Ayurvedic* classics, the seven important factors (*Saptako Dravya Samgraha*) are related to *kushtha* .Three *Dosha*(*Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*) and four *Dushya* (*Twak*, *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, *Ambu*) are involved under the pathology of skin disease.¹¹ .

According to *SushrutaSamhita*, due to *NidanaSevan* vitiated *Pitta* and *KaphaDosha* with help of vitiated *VayuDosha* comes in contact with *Dushya* and they cause *Mandala* at affected part¹².

Holistic Approach for Management of Dermatitis:

In *ayurvedic* classics the treatment of all diseases is comprised mainly of three modalities , first and foremost is *Shodhana* therapy (Biopurification) which is very much unique concept of *ayurveda*. The second part is *Shamana* (use of various Herbo-minerals compositions) and the last modality is *Nidana parivarjanam* (avoidance of causative factors according to *ayurveda*)¹³.

Mode of action of all modalities:

***Shodhana* Therapy (Bio-Purification):**

Acharya charka has mentioned that in the state of *Bahudosha* (excessive vitiated *doshik* condition) condition of *vicharchika* the *sodhana* therapy should be given to the patient many times without threatening life¹⁴. According to *Dosha Pradhanata Acharya Charaka* mentioned *Sarpi Pana* in *Vata Dosha*, *Vamana Karma* in *Kapha Dosha*, *Virechana* and *Raktamokshana* in *Pitta Dosha Pradhanya*¹⁵.

Shodhana Karma can be performed after its *Purvakarma*. By *Purvakarma* (*Snehana*, *Swedana*) *Dosha* becomes *Shithila* and ready to remove outside from body.

vicharchika is *kapha* dominant disease despite of its *Tridoshaja* origin hence first *karma* is *vamana karma*. *Vamana* removes vitiated *Kapha* from whole body through upper part of elementary canal because of its *prabhava*.¹⁶ As per *Ayurvedic* texts *Kapha* is one of the main vitiated *Dosha* in *vicharchika*. So *Vamana* is the best for excreting vitiated *Kapha* from body in *vicharchika*. Considering the importance of *Vamana* in relieving the symptoms of dermatitis, *Acharya Sushruta* has suggested to perform it every 15 days¹⁷.

Virechana removes vitiated *Pitta Dosha* from whole body through lower part of elementary canal¹⁸. *Pitta Dosha* resides in *Rakta Dhatu*. Therefore the purificative measures of *Pitta Dosha*, also improve the

Rakta Dhatu. In *Charaka Samhita* it is mentioned that *khushtha* is due to *Rakta Dushti*¹⁹. The line of treatment of *Raktaja Roga* :

कुर्यात् शोणितरोगेषु रक्तपित्तहरीं क्रियाम् ।

विरेकं उपवसं च सावणं शोणितस्य च ||(ch.su.24/18)²⁰

This way *Virechana* and *raktamokshan* can apply for *RaktaShuddhi* (Blood purification) purpose in *khushtha*. So *Acharya Sushruta* has suggested performing *Virechana* every one month and *raktamokshana* at every six month or twice a year²¹.

Shaman Therapy:

This is very much important in maintaining the homeostasis in balance as it is also known as *Prakrutisthapan* and *Prayyschita*²². *Shaman chikitsa* is mainly divided in three groups²³.

Daivvypashray-

Daiva means deeds done in previous life (*Puryjanma*). It can be the cause of some diseases also and these types of diseases are named as *Karmaja Roga*. Treatment given by the physician in form of medicine might not work as expected²⁴ that is why in this situation we have to use *daivavypasraya chikitsa* like mantra chanting or offering prayers or *upvasa*, *prayashchita* etc²⁵. *Acharya vagabhatta* specially mentioned this treatment in *khushtha*.

Yuktivypashraya:

Correct implementation of *Ahardravya* (articles those are ingested by mouth), and *Aushadhravya* (medicines) is known as *Yuktivypashraya*²⁶. It can be opposite to cause, disease or both (i.e. *hetuviprita*, *vyadhiviprita*, *ubhayaviprita* or *hetu*, *vyadhi*, *ubhayavipreetarthkari*).²⁷

Satvavajaya

Satva (i.e. *mana*/ mind) is *samvayi* (inseparable) to skin²⁸. That is why any insult to skin affects the *satva* very badly. *Satvavaiay chikitsa* means-*Punarahitavyaoarthebhyomanonighraha*²⁹.

Nidana parivarjanam

Nidana parivarjanam (Avoidance of Causative Factor) is very much of importance because it helps in maintaining the balance between the three physiological factors known as *vata*, *pitta*, *kapha*. *Nidana sevana* (exposure to causative factors) vitiates the *Doshas* from their normal state which lead to disease condition. *Acharya shustruta* says that *Nidana parivarjanam* is equivalent to treatment in short³⁰

Discussion:

Shodhana is foremost part of the management of the diseases. So that *Acharyas* has advised to perform all the *Panchakarma* purificative procedure again and again³¹. Among all the five type of *Panchakarma*, *Vamana* and *Virechana* are major purifying Karma, which excrete the elevated *Kapha* and *Pitta Dosha*³² as well do *Anulomana* of *Vayu* too³³.

Acharya Charaka mentioned as “*Dirgharoganam*”³⁴ that means it is long lasting disease and practically recurrence of *vicharchika* is also observed.

If the *Dosha* are pacified with *Langhana* or *Pachana* therapy, there may be chances of recurrences of that disease. But if they are removed with *Samshodhana*, there is no possibility of its recurrence. Similarly if bio-purification (*Vamana* and *Virechana*) is performed prior to *Shamana* therapy recurrence chances can be reduced considerably³⁵.

Moreover, if the *Shamana* treatment is given after the proper *Shodhan*, it provides better effect. So that the *Ayurvedic* classics emphasize on purification with the example to color the cloth. If the cloth is coloured without its washing, it is not properly coloured while if it is done with its proper washing, it takes colors appropriately. Similarly, medicine given after the *Urdhvaga* and *AdhogaShuddhi* or *Ubhaya Marga Shuddhi*, will provide desirable effect³⁶.

Shamana therapy after *shodhana* gives best result if we follow the above written pattern. It is practically seen that merely prescribing medicines without taking account of all aspects which are discussed in

above portion may fail treatment. Three aspects of *shamana* are very much important as they help in maintaining the homeostasis. Acharya acharaka indicated that the treatment with “*Tikta rasapradhanadravya*” is best for *shamana* therapy of *khustha Chikitsa*³⁷.

Nidana parivarjanam has been taken by the ancient scholars as the treatment in brief³⁸.

Conclusion:

This above description clearly indicates that *shodhana* (biopurification) therapy, *shamana* therapy and *Nidana parivarjanam* is complete treatment of skin diseases which are very much hard to treat. If we do not take account of all aspects of therapy we could not be able to treat any skin problem effectively.

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